

Effect of Promotional Tool on Product Development in Food and Beverages Industry in Enugu State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study evaluated the effect of promotional tool on product development in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria. The Specific Objectives were to: examine the effect of advertising on the physical expansion of products and determined the extent the effect of sales promotions on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria. The area of the study was Enugu State. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 912 staff was used. The adequate sample size of 270, using Freund and William's statistic formula at 5 percent margin of error was used. 244staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed using Likert Scale and the hypotheses using Z test. The findings indicated Advertising had significant positive effect on the physical expansion of products, $Z(95, n = 224), 5.981 < 8.710 = p < 0.05$ and sales promotions had significant positive effect on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria $Z(95, n = 224), 7.082 < 8.419 = p < 0.05$. The study concluded that advertisements and sales promotion had significant positive effect on physical expansion and improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria. The study recommended among others that Advertising in the organisation should not be seen as an ordinary assignment which can be assigned to any employee, rather it should be embraced with all seriousness and assigned to individuals who are capable of carrying out the duty efficiently.

Keywords *Product Development; Food and Beverages Industry; Enugu State*

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Introduction

Promotion is the aspect of marketing that involves delivery of company, brand or product messages to target customers. Traditional methods of promotion, like print and television ads, are nowadays augmented by new avenues of messaging made possible by digital communications. Several tools are used by companies to aid the delivery of both paid and unpaid promotional methods. Each tool contributes a different way to reach customers and achieve communication objectives.

Manufacturing firms all around the world have experienced challenges in their daily operations, most notably in the sector where companies are continuously grappling with a steady drop in consumer patronage as a result of the worldwide pandemic's impact (Lynch, 2018). Low product turnover, poor facilities, purchasing and supply chain, inadequate marketing, safety and quality of goods are just a few of the issues that these businesses face. Agriculture, manufacture and distribution of food items, canvassing and selling of commodities in general are all part of the Foods and Beverages industry globally (Mandall and Rosenberg, 2021). Any nation's progress cannot be discussed without mentioning the contribution of the Foods and Beverage industry, which has constantly seen an increase in the growth of food up to 3700 producers with an employment rate of more than 147,000 employees.

The Foods and Beverages sector in the United States of America (USA) employs around 21,000 people and generates approximately \$60 billion in revenue. According to Ellen, California is one of the top five food-producing states in the United States, leading in the production of raw milk, almonds worldwide, vegetables, fruits, nuts, and tomato processing, with over 6,000 farms around the state. In Kenya, the manufacturing sector expanded at a rate of 3.5 percent in 2015 and 3.2 percent in 2014, contributing 10.3 percent to GDP, but in South Africa, the manufacturing sector accounts for 14 percent of the country's economy, down from 20 percent in 1994 (Uloko, 2019). In Nigeria, the food and beverage sector is made up of small, medium, and international firms that are increasingly being viewed as a niche in Africa's overall markets (Uloko, 2019). Food and beverage firms in Nigeria have discovered that processed foods are consumed at a rate of 37.6 per-cent, followed by protein at 32.4 percent, and cereals at 30 percent (Ejabefio, 2017). To make these food categories and commodities available to their end consumers through middlemen, a strong advertising approach will be perfect, highlighting the significance of this research.

The frequent occurrence of gaps in marketing communications among farmers and ultimate customers has an impact on the production level of food and beverage businesses, according to Oni and Yeboah (2012). This indicates that in order to be known in the market, companies must always build awareness through efficient sales marketing of their goods and features, as well as their related pricing, to all stakeholders. This, without a doubt, will increase consumer patronage. Consumer views and attitudes substantially impact their purchase decisions, even if some of these perceptions and attitudes regarding an organization's image and products are incorrect. There is therefore, the need for organizations to influence consumers and customers through any or integration of their marketing communications mix in order to change these wrong perceptions and attitudes (Bridges, et. al., 2016).

Companies in the food and beverage sector in Nigeria have faced fierce rivalry. Many of these businesses have turned to sales marketing to drive sales traffic to their brands. As a result, literature on sales promotion has demonstrated that it has a substantial influence on consumer patronage (Chandon, Wansink, & Laurent, 2011). Price reductions, coupons, and extra product packs appear to have influenced consumers positively in their purchases of goods and services, but in some cases, they simply do not work due to influencing factors such as the culture in which the consumer finds himself/herself, the consumer's social life, the consumer's psychological makeup, and personal considerations. These elements tend to steer customers in specific directions during the decision-making process. Therefore, this study seeks to examine the effect of promotional tools in marketing new products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Statement of Problem

Sales promotion efforts, which include both monetary and non-monetary incentives are critical for drawing customers' attention to her goods and services, increasing customer patronage, and overcoming competitive obstacles. Strenuous rivalry among rivals in Nigeria's Foods and Beverage businesses has resulted in the use of various marketing strategies in order to become the market leader several firms in the food and beverage industry use sales promotion strategies all around the world to outsmart their competitors.

However, sales promotion, as excellent as it is in terms of giving numerous incentives designed to encourage quick sales and greater purchases by clients, is limited in time. Regardless of the aforementioned aspects of sales promotion, many consumers seek out other rivals due to unsatisfactory services, a desire for greater promotional incentives, and a lack of appropriate capacity to provide value to customers' demands, therefore increasing customer turn over.

Foods and beverage companies both at home and abroad are facing challenges such as food manufacturing and processing, poor amenities, purchasing and supply chain, insufficient promotions, safety and quality of goods, and so on, implying the timely intervention of all interested parties such as stakeholders, private and public sector. This study seeks to use this research topic "the effect of promotional tools in marketing new products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria" to resolved the challenges food and beverages industries face to the minimum.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the Effect of promotional tool on product development in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria. The Specific Objectives were to:

- i. Examine the effect of advertising on the physical expansion of products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria.
- ii. Determined the extent the effect of sales promotions on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

- i. Examine the effect of advertising on the physical expansion of products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria.
- ii. Determined the extent the effect of sales promotions on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

- i. Advertising has effect on the physical expansion of products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria.
- ii. Sales promotions have effect on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Significance of the study

The study will be of great impact to business owners, managers and employees. It will serve as an eye opener to organizations in other to observe existing and incurring loopholes in the organizations which can hinder the growth of the organization and sales. The study will also serve as an empirical literature to future studies.

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study covered the effect of promotional tool on product development in food and beverages industry in Enugu State, Nigeria. The components issues were: Advertising and the physical expansion of products; and Sales promotions and improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Related Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Promotion

Promotion represents the collection of all elements in an organizations marketing mix that facilitate exchanges by establishing shared meaning with the organizations customers or clients (Makale, 2014). Promotion in marketing is aimed at creating an awareness of the organization and its products and/or services in order to increase sales and make a profit. The sender (organization) conveys messages about the organizations products and/or services to the receiver (customer) in order to persuade the customer to buy the organizations products or to make use of its services. In order to create a lasting relationship, messages focus on the brand, customers" needs and the organizations commitment to society. A brand is the sum of all emotions, thoughts and recognitions that people in the target audience have about an organization (McNamara, 2011).

Promotional Tools

Promotions tools offer creative ways for businesses to market their goods or services. These tools can be effective in highlighting and increasing awareness of new brands, encouraging customer loyalty, increasing sales of a particular item or a combination of these benefits. There are many of these tools available, and it's helpful to research them to know which ones would be best to market and promote goods and services. Promotional tools are strategies, methods or resources that compel consumers to buy a product or service. Many marketing and advertising professionals use them to raise awareness of a new product or increase sales of a particular item or service. Professionals can also use these tools as part of a long-term, comprehensive marketing strategy. A company may choose one promotional tool over another based on different factors, such as the tool's availability, performance and profitability.

Components of Promotional Tools used in the Study

Advertising

Advertising is the arm of marketing concerned with sending messages to customers via traditionally one-way communication media (David, 2020). Advertisements can be created to appeal to a mass audience or a select target niche. Advertising can have a significant impact on the success of small and large businesses alike, and a sizable industry exists specifically to conceptualize, create and distribute advertisements. Advertisements can be placed on a variety of media. Television, radio, magazines and newspapers dominated the advertising world throughout the 20th century, but the Internet has continued to gain popularity among advertisers since its initial rapid growth in the 1990s. Advertising is not limited to media options; ads can be placed in physical locations, such as billboards and shop windows, as well. Businesses now face great competition in enhancing the influence of their advertising to create awareness, drive sales, maintain market share and establish brand identity (Hall, 2019).

Sales Promotions

Sales are the lifeblood of any business, without sales there would be no business in the first place; therefore sales promotion strategy is very important for organizations that want to succeed. Sales promotion can be specific tool of the marketing strategy of an organization because of increasing level of competition and costs advertisement (Kotler, 2016). The primary objective of a sales promotion is to improve an organization's sales by predicting and modifying their target customers purchasing behaviour and patterns. Sales promotion is very essential in product marketing as it helps to draw new customers while at the same time retaining the existing ones (Smriti, 2020). The value of sales promotion has been growing in recent years. Currently the money spent on sales promotion is equivalent to the amount spent on advertisement. The sales promotion as a product marketing strategy increases due to the changes in the marketing environment and the thinking of new ideas for creating a favourable condition of selling, promoting sales and future expansion of sales (Shreyasi, 2020).

Product

A product is the relevant output of organizations activities often in form of a goods, service, idea or combination of the three. Each product has a useful life after which it needs replacement, and a life cycle after which it has to be re-invented. In general, a product means something which is produced by labor or effort. In marketing, a product is offered towards the customers' needs and wants and satisfies the customer. A product may be tangible or intangible, liquid or non-liquid, transferable or non-transferable. Companies or organizations offer their product for selling and earning products. Every product has a product life cycle from its development (Hasan, 2023). Product quality earns customer loyalty, helps establish brand recognition and manages costs. *Product knowledge is the most important tool for sales.* A product is a good can be a physical object that instantly becomes yours to own once purchased. One thing to remember about products is that they can be tangible or intangible. A tangible product is generally a physical object that you can touch and perceive directly (Ntloko, 2020).

Development

Development means an increase in the size or pace of the economy such that more products and services are produced. Conventionally, a common assumption has been that, if an economy generates more products and services, then humans will enjoy a higher standard of living. The aim of many conventional approaches to development has been to increase the size of the economy (economic growth) in order to increase the output of products and services. Development means "improvement in country's economic and social conditions". More specially, it refers to improvements in way of managing an area's natural and human resources (Shah, 2021).

Product Development

Product developments are the steps involved in creating a product. It is a series of steps that includes the conceptualization, design, development and marketing of newly created or newly rebranded goods or services. Product development typically refers to all stages involved in bringing a product from concept or idea through market release and beyond. In other words, product development incorporates a product's entire journey (Product, 2023). Product development includes a product's entire journey from the initial idea to after its market release. The objective of product development from a business standpoint is to cultivate, maintain and increase a company's market share by satisfying consumer demand (Gillis, 2023).

Components of Product Development

Physical Expansion of Products

Product expansion is a strategy used by most organization to expand their products and bring it to the notice of the customers. An expansion strategy is a plan of action that a business or organization implements to grow its operations, increase its market share, and achieve its long-term goals. Physical expansion of products involves selling more of existing products or services to current customer base or expanding reach within the current market. Product expansion requires intensive planning to ensure that the expected returns outweigh the costs and risks involved. Principles of operations strategy can guide a business throughout the physical product expansion process (Hartman, 2023). Business Expansion is a stage where the business reaches the point for growth and seeks out for additional options to generate more profit. Different forms of business expansion include opening in another location, adding sales employees, increased marketing, adding franchisees, forming an alliance, offering new products or services, entering new markets, merging with or acquiring another business, expanding globally and expanding through the internet (Attract, 2023).

Improvement in Products

Quality improvement is the framework used to systematically improve processes and systems. Quality refers to the degree of excellence of something. Quality Improvement means a focus on activities to improve performance above minimum standards and reasonably expected levels of performance, quality and practice (Chelsea, 2021). Quality improvement is a systematic, formal approach to the analysis of practice performance and efforts to improve performance. Quality improvement refers to the combined and unceasing efforts of everybody in a company to

make everything about it, especially its production process, better. It is a systematic approach to the elimination or reduction of rework, waste, and losses in the production process (MBN, 2021).

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Source: Researcher; 2023

Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by Means-end theory by Olson and Reynolds (1983)

Means-End Theory

The study was anchored on the Means-End Theory, because it asserts that people make choices about a product, service or issue in a manner that taps into four dimensions: attributes benefits, emotions and personal values. This theory was developed by Olson and Reynolds 1983. The Means-End Chain Theory (MEC) is a value-based, cognitive model that facilitates the better understanding of decision-making and consumer behaviour. It connects the tangible attributes of a product (the means) to highly abstract and intangible personal and emotional values (the ends) (Olson and Reynolds, 2001). The means-end theory is a highly regarded mental model for understanding consumer decision-making. It is proposed that customers relate to products and services at three levels: attributes (components), consequences, and values (goals) (Meral and Ernest, 2014). Customer value is understood as one of the constructs that best explains consumer decision making. Its proposal is to understand how consumers translate product or service characteristics and consequences of use into personal self-relevant values. The means-end theory is a way of systematically thinking in this hierarchical representation.

Empirical Review

Effect of Advertising on the Physical Expansion of Products

Agbeja, Adalakun and Akinyemi (2015) conducted Analysis of the Effect of Advertising on Sales and Profitability of Company. The paper assessed the effect of advertising on sales and profitability of a company. The SPSS software package was used to adequately verify the data collected for this study. The regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis of the variables that were involved in this study in order to analyze the data. The paper concludes that there exists a significant relationship between marketing expenses and profitability of the firm and also there exists a significant relationship between turnover and marketing expenses of the firm. The paper suggests that a company should maintain a cost-effective system of advertising in which high quality personnel is a major component. The advertising system should be controlled by a mechanism that fosters the good reputation of the company and its products.

Sanjeet, Gagan and Mandeep (2018) wrote on the causal effect of advertisement on profit and sales. The present study evaluates the relationship between advertisement expenditure, sales revenue and the profits of companies, which are listed in the National Stock Exchange (NSE). Originality – In the past researchers evaluated the impact of sales on advertisement or sales. The present research will study the impact of the advertisement expenditure, sales revenue and the profits on each other. There is a need of this study Research Method – The tools used for the analysis are descriptive statistics, unit root test, granger causality, VAR (Vector Auto Regression) and Variance Decomposition. Findings – The findings of the research shows that there is a visible impact of the previous years

sales on the sale of current year as well as the sale impact the advertisement and profit as well. On the other hand the profit impacts the advertisement.

Abdullahi et al. (2019) conducted research on the impact of advertising as a promotional tool on new product development (a case study of Unilever Nigeria plc, Abuja). The aim of this study is to explore the role of advertising as a promotional tool for marketing a new product. A case study of Unilever Nigeria plc. An attempt was made to evaluate the effectiveness or role of advertising as one of the promotional mix element used by Unilever Nigeria Plc Abuja. This study is quantitative in nature as 20 questionnaires were handout to the respondents and non probability sampling techniques was adopted, Hypotheses was formulated and tested with the use of Chi-square which shows that there exists relationship between the advertising expenditure and the annual turnover, and that advertising has a significant effect on the development. It also revealed that the choice of the right media selection can affect the effectiveness of the message of advertising. It was recommended that for the effective sales of product, appropriate plan and design of the message of advertising should be done before caring out the practice of advertising in an Organization; also the selection of the right media is also very important for the effectiveness of the use of advertising.

Effect of Sales Promotions on Improvement in Products

Pembi, Fudamu, and Ibrahim (2017) studied the impact of sales promotional strategies on organizational performance in Nigeria. The objectives of this study are to examine the impact of sales promotional strategies on organizational performance with reference to Flour Mills Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria. The population of this study was carved out of the entire staff of the Flour Mills of Nigeria Maiduguri, Borno State branch cutting across the Top, Middle and lower level management. The study employed both the primary and secondary sources of data collection. Questionnaires were administered to twenty (20) staff using random sampling techniques. The data collected were subjected to descriptive statistics such as percentage analysis in order to analyze the data and regression analyses were used for testing hypotheses. The result signifies that sales promotional strategies have positive and significant effects on organizational performance.

Uloko, (2019) assessed the impact of promotion on the profitability of the Nigeria Bottling Company Plc, Enugu Plant. The population of the study was made up of 56 management staff drawn from marketing, sales and accounting/finance departments of the company. Employing a census technique, the whole population of 56 management staff constituted the sample size of the study and data obtained from the 56 copies of the questionnaire were presented using descriptive statistics whereas, multiple regression analysis with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was conducted to test both the company's financial statement from the year 2003 to 2012 and the hypotheses. The findings from data analysis of company's financial statement shows that, profit is slightly influenced by the variables of sales income not necessary cost of promotion, while the results of the hypotheses testing indicated that, rebates have no significant impact on profitability; sales promotion has a significant impact on profitability; personal selling has no significant impact on profitability; public relations have a significant impact on profitability. The need for an organization to properly coordinate its promotional strategies to achieve a clear consistent and competitive message about itself and its products has become an issue of concern to every result driving firm. The study concluded that, promotion is an important tool that helps companies to improve their profitability.

Orji, and Ahungwa, (2020) examine the effects of sales promotion on the consumer buying behavior of food seasoning among Nigerian households using Nestle Nigeria Plc Maggi NAIJA POT brand as a case study. The study employed cross sectional research design and the population consists of consumers of Nestle product (Maggi seasoning) in Bwari Area Council, Abuja. The sample size is 246 determined using Topman's formula. Primary data was used through administration of questionnaire and regression analysis was used to test the relationship between the study variables. The findings revealed that most of the consumers enjoy the rebates which influence their decision before, during and after the purchase; there is a positive effect of free trial and free gift on consumer buying behavior of Maggi NAIJAPOT in Bwari Area Council, Abuja. The study concluded that that sales promotion through rebates, free trial and free gifts is one significant tool marketing companies should give attention to in order to influence their consumers' buying behavior.

Michael (2021) carried research on the effect of sales promotion on marketing of cocacola drinks in Anambra State. This study examined the effect of sales promotion on the marketing of Coca-Cola drinks in Anambra State. The major aim of the study is to ascertain the effect of Personal selling, Rebates trade and discounts on the marketing of Coca-Cola drink in Anambra State. This study adopted a descriptive survey design. This study is carried out in Onitsha Anambra State. The researcher made use of primary sources. The population of the study comprises all the customers in Onitsha. The population is unknown (infinite). The sample size is 368 obtain by using Topman's non-parametric sample size determination formula. The study used test-retest and Cronbach Alpha method in order to affirm the reliability of the research instruments. The data for this study were collected by means of questionnaire and persona; interview. Frequency tables and percentage analysis were used to present quantitative data in form of tables. The study also employed Multiple Regression Analysis. The results show that personal selling has significant effect on marketing of Coca-Cola drink in Anambra State. Rebates have significant effect on marketing of Coca-Cola drink in Anambra State. Trade discounts have significant effect on marketing of Coca-Cola drink in Anambra State. The study concludes that sales promotion has significant positive effect on the marketing of Coca-Cola drink in Anambra State.

George, Bamidele, and Damilola (2022) conducted research on the sales promotion and customer patronage of selected food and beverages companies in Lagos State Nigeria. Several firms in the food and beverage industry use sales promotion strategies all around the world to outsmart their competitors. However, sales promotion, as excellent as it is in terms of giving numerous incentives designed to encourage quick sales and greater purchases by clients, is limited in time. Regardless of the aforementioned aspects of sales promotion, many consumers seek out other rivals due to unsatisfactory services, a desire for greater promotional incentives, and a lack of appropriate capacity to provide value to customers' demands, therefore increasing customer turnover. This paper investigated the effect of sales promotion tools such as free sample, rebate, contest and price discount on customer patronage of the selected Food and Beverages Companies in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. The total population of the study is 3502 staffs of the selected food and beverage firms operating in Lagos State, Nigeria. Taro Yamane sample size calculation technique to estimate the sample size of the population to determine the sample size of the study. A validated questionnaire was administered and a total of 344 retrieved for analysis. The data collected were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. Findings revealed that sales promotion tools significantly affect customer patronage in the selected Food and Beverages Companies in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Gap in Empirical Review

The few studies done were carried outside Effect of promotional tool on product development in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria and did not focus to best of my knowledge on advertising and the physical expansion of products and sales promotions on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria. Most of the studies reviewed analysed their data through A purposeful sampling technique, Descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential statistics, Purposive Sampling technique, Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient, Multiple sampling technique, Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method, Simple linear regression and Pearson correlation coefficient (r) while the present study made use of Pearson correlation coefficient (r) to test the hypotheses. Therefore, the study aimed at filling the research gap by evaluating the effect of promotional tool on product development of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria.

Methodology

The area of the study was Enugu metropolis, Enugu state. Five (5) food and beverage manufacturing firms were selected. The choice of these firms was due to high number of staff, Capital base above 10 million naira. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. A total population of 912 selected staff of the study organisations. The sample size of 270 was drawn using Freund and William's formula at 5 percent error margin. Two hundred and twenty-four (224) staff returned the questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 83 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient

(r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.710 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z – test statistic tool.

Data Presentation

The effect of advertising on the physical expansion of products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

Table 1: Responses on the effect of advertising on the physical expansion of products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision	
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X			
1	Advertisement increases awareness of products and service	540	148	96	52	21	857	3.83	1.382	Agree	
		108	37	32	26	21	224				
		48.2	16.5	14.3	11.6	9.4	100%				
2	Producing an increase in sales are as result of advertising.	555	148	90	54	19	866	3.87	1.366	Agree	
		111	37	30	27	19	224				
		49.6	6.5	13.4	12.1	8.5	100%				
3	Increase in familiarity and trust between organisation and their customers was through advertising.	500	148	117	48	24	837	3.74	1.397	Agree	
		100	37	39	24	24	224				
		44.6	16.5	17.4	10.7	10.7	100%				
4	Potential customer seeing multiple ads about the products considers the organization a trusted brand.	475	224	99	34	23	848	3.82	1.332	Agree	
		95	56	33	17	23	224				
		42.4	25.0	14.7	7.6	10.3	100%				
5	The elimination of middleman enhanced expansion of the market.	580	216	66	36	14	912	4.07	1.225	Agree	
		116	54	22	18	14	224				
		51.8	24.1	9.8	8.0	6.3	100%				
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.866	1.340	4	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 1, 145 respondents out of 224 representing 64.7 percent agreed that advertisement increases awareness of products and service with mean score 3.83 and standard deviation of 1.382. Producing an increase in sales are as result of advertising 148 respondents representing 66.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.87 and standard deviation of 1.366. Increase in familiarity and trust between organisation and their customers was through advertising 137 respondents representing 61.1 percent agreed with mean score of 3.74 and standard deviation of 1.397. Potential customer seeing multiple ads about the products considers the organization a trusted brand 151 respondents representing 67.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.82 and 1.332. The elimination of middleman enhanced expansion of the market 170 respondents representing 75.9 percent agreed with a mean score of 4.07 and standard deviation 1.225.

The extent the effect of sales promotions on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

Table 2: Responses on the extent the effect of sales promotions on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Sales promotion strategy increases interest or demand in the products	475 95 42.4	268 67 29.9	54 18 8.0	58 29 12.9	15 15 6.7	870 224 100%	3.88	1.272	Agree
2	The use of sales promotion tries to prompt a target segments to show interest in the products.	490 98 43.8	292 73 32.6	57 19 8.5	16 8 3.6	26 26 11.6	881 224 100%	3.93	1.309	Agree
3	Improvement in product availability is enhanced by sales promotion.	605 121 54.0	244 61 27.2	54 18 8.0	12 6 2.7	18 18 8.0	933 224 100%	4.17	1.196	Agree
4	Push and pull strategies focuses on pushing a product towards the audience and increase in productivity.	545 107 47.8	288 72 32.1	39 13 5.8	36 18 8.0	14 14 6.3	922 224 100%	4.07	1.192	Agree
5	Sales promotion encourages repeat of the business.	400 80 35.7	348 87 38.8	39 13 5.8	54 27 12.1	17 17 7.6	858 224 100%	3.83	1.248	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.976	1.2434	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Table 2, 162 respondents out of 224 representing 72.3 percent agreed that Sales promotion strategy increases interest or demand in the products with mean score 3.88 and standard deviation of 1.272. The use of sales promotion tries to prompt a target segments to show interest in the products 171 respondents representing 76.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.93 and standard deviation of 1.309. Improvement in product availability is enhanced by sales promotion 182 respondents representing 81.2 percent agreed with mean score of 4.17 and standard deviation of 1.196. Push and pull strategies focuses on pushing a product towards the audience and increase in productivity 179 respondents representing 79.9 percent agreed with mean score of 4.07 and 1.192. Sales promotion encourages repeat of the business 167 respondents representing 74.5 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.83 and standard deviation 1.248.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypotheses one: Advertising has effect on the physical expansion of products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

Table 3: Z-test on advertising has effect on the physical expansion of products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test						
		Advertisement increases awareness of products and service	Producing an increase in sales are as result of advertising.	Increase in familiarity and trust between organisation and their customers was through advertising.	Potential customer seeing multiple ads about the products considers the organization a trusted brand.	The elimination of middleman enhanced expansion of the market.
N		224	224	224	224	224
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.482	.496	.446	.424	.518
	Positive	.094	.085	.107	.103	.063
	Negative	-.482	-.496	-.446	-.424	-.518
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		7.216	7.416	6.682	6.347	7.751
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $6.347 < 7.751$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that advertising had significant positive effect on the physical expansion of products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $5.981 < 8.710$ against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that advertising had significant positive effect on the physical expansion of products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

Hypotheses two: Sales promotions have effect on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

Table 4: Z-test on sales promotions has effect on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test						
		Sales promotion strategy increases interest or demand in the products.	The use of sales promotion tries to prompt a target segments to show interest in the products	Improvement in product availability is enhanced by sales promotion	Push and pull strategies focuses on pushing a product towards the audience and increase in productivity.	Sales promotion encourages repeat of the business.
N		224	224	224	224	224
Uniform Parameter $s^{a,b}$	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.473	.513	.563	.549	.496
	Positive	.067	.116	.080	.063	.076
	Negative	-.473	-.513	-.563	-.549	-.496
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		7.082	7.684	8.419	8.218	7.416
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value ranges from $.7.082 < .8.419$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that sales promotions had significant positive effect on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value ranges from $.7.082 < .8.419$ against the critical Z- value of $.000$ (2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that sales promotions had significant positive effect on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

Test of Hypotheses

Advertising had significant positive effect on the physical expansion of products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria

Hypotheses one showed that the calculated Z- value ranges from $5.981 < 8.710$ against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that advertising had significant positive effect on the physical expansion of products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria. In support of these hypotheses, Abdullahi et. al, (2019) conducted a research on the impact of advertising as a promotional tool on new product development (a case study of Unilever Nigeria plc, Abuja). The aim of this study is to explore the role of advertising as a promotional tool for marketing a new product. A case study of Unilever Nigeria plc. An attempt was made to evaluate the effectiveness or role of advertising as one of the promotional mix elements used by Unilever Nigeria Plc Abuja. Hypotheses was formulated and tested with the use of Chi-square which shows that there exists relationship between the advertising expenditure and the annual turnover, and that advertising has a significant effect on the development. It also revealed that the choice of the right media selection can affect the effectiveness of the message of advertising. It was recommended that for the effective sales of product, appropriate plan and design of the message of advertising should be done before carrying out the practice of advertising in an Organisation; also, the selection of the right media is also very important for the effectiveness of the use of advertising.

Sales promotions had significant positive effect on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu State, Nigeria

Hypotheses two revealed the calculated Z- value ranges from $.7.082 < .8.419$ against the critical Z- value of .000(2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that sales promotions had significant positive effect on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria. George, Bamidele, and Damilola (2022) conducted a research on the Sales Promotion and Customer Patronage of Selected Food and Beverages Companies in Lagos State Nigeria. Several firms in the food and beverage industry use sales promotion strategies all around the world to outsmart their competitors. However, sales promotion, as excellent as it is in terms of giving numerous incentives designed to encourage quick sales and greater purchases by clients, is limited in time. Regardless of the aforementioned aspects of sales promotion, many consumers seek out other rivals due to unsatisfactory services, a desire for greater promotional incentives, and a lack of appropriate capacity to provide value to customers' demands, therefore increasing customer turnover. Findings revealed that sales promotion tools significantly affect customer patronage in the selected Food and Beverages Companies in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Summary of findings

The following findings were made by the study;

- i. Advertising had significant positive effect on the physical expansion of products in food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria $Z(95, n = 224), 5.981 < 8.710 = p. < 0.05$
- ii. Sales promotions had significant positive effect on improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria $Z(95, n = 224), .7.082 < .8.419 = p. < 0.05$

Conclusion

The study concludes that advertisements and sales promotion had significant positive effect on physical expansion and improvement in products of food and beverages industry in Enugu state, Nigeria. Promotion in marketing is aimed at creating an awareness of the organization and its products and/or services in order to increase sales and make a profit. Promotion is the voice of every organisation which helps to announce the presence/ existence of the product to clients. Having a full-proof and well-thought-out promotional strategy and marketing plan helps to identify different segments of consumers in the market and offer suitable solutions for clients.

Recommendations

The study recommends that

- i. Advertising in the organisation should not be seen as an ordinary assignment which can be assigned to any employee, rather it should be embraced with all seriousness and assigned to individuals who are capable of carrying out the duty efficiently.
- ii. Organizations should not only focus on advertising its product but should also ensure that there is room for consumer feedback which will help to enhance the product.

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